

Bayesian Learning of Spatiotemporal Source Distribution for Beached Microplastic in the United States Gulf Coast

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Abstract

Over the last several decades, plastic waste has gradually accumulated while slowly degrading in terrestrial and oceanic environments. Recently, there has been an increased effort to identify the possible sources of plastic to understand how they affect vulnerable beaches. This is of particular concern in the Gulf Coast of the United States due to the presence of oil, natural gas, and plastic production. In this study, we expand upon existing Bayesian plastic attribution models and develop a rigorous statistical framework to map observed beached microplastics to their sources. Within this framework, we combine Lagrangian backtracking simulations of floating particles using nurdle beaching data with estimates of plastic input from coastlines, rivers, and fisheries. This allows us to build a spatiotemporal source-to-sink distribution for microplastic beached in the Gulf states. We infer that the main sources of microplastics found on beaches throughout the region are centered around New Orleans, Galveston Bay, Corpus Christi, Mérida, the Grijalva and Pearl Rivers, as well as from fishing activities around the Mississippi River Delta. We also find strong seasonal effects of microplastic transport in the Gulf caused by the time-varying ocean currents and tourism.

Key Words: Backtracking simulations, Lagrangian ocean analysis framework, Nurdle, Virtual particles

1. Introduction

Since the introduction of synthetic polymers in the 1950s, plastic waste has accumulated at increasing rates in terrestrial and oceanic environments. Global plastic production reached 390.7 million metric tons in 2021, a nearly 780% increase from 1975 (PlasticsEurope, 2015, 2022). In 2010, the estimated annual flux of plastic waste from land into the ocean was approximately 4.8-12.7 million metric tons, projected to increase nearly 10-fold by 2025 (Jambeck et al., 2015). In 2015, the global estimate of floating plastics at sea was 5.25 trillion plastic pieces weighing 268,940 metric tons (Eriksen et al., 2014) ranging in sizes from meters to nanometers. Only a small portion of the plastic waste that enters marine environments is positively buoyant and continues floating in the ocean (Lebreton and Andrady, 2019). The remaining plastic waste either sinks to the ocean floor, is consumed by marine organisms, or beached on coasts. Therefore, plastic debris poses a significant risk for marine and terrestrial ecosystems (Amobonye et al., 2021) and our health and well-being (Vethaak and Legler, 2021).

Over the past few decades, numerous studies have estimated the global distribution of plastics, focusing on microplastics (sizes <5mm). Microplastics are of more significant environmental concern due to their size and variable distribution in marine and terrestrial environments making survey, collection, removal, and recycling difficult. Microplastic can come in a variety of shapes, sizes, and polymers. They are either purposely produced to create other plastic products (primary microplastics) or are the by-products of environmental degradation (secondary microplastics). Globally, microplastics account for only a small portion of floating plastic marine debris, about 13.2% of the total floating plastic in the ocean (Lebreton et al., 2019). Global estimates are highly uncertain due to the variation in sampling methods, in-situ measurement types, laboratory experiments, and data sources (Van Sebille et al., 2020), which makes comparing and combining data on microplastics a complex exercise and can result in high levels of uncertainty.

It is important to note that most global studies estimating microplastic presence in the open ocean refer to secondary microplastics. Therefore, most models underestimate microplastics' abundance (or mass) by potentially a significant margin (Boucher and Friot, 2017; Eriksen et al., 2014; Van Sebille et al., 2015). Quantifying the abundance of primary microplastics in isolation is challenging due to various sources and transport methods into marine environments. According to Boucher and Friot (2017), between 15 and 31% of all floating plastic debris in the ocean could originate from primary sources. In some countries, the abundance of microplastics outweighs larger plastic sizes (> 5mm). Overall, understanding the distribution of plastic sizes and their sources is an ongoing research effort. While regional studies on microplastics are abundant in literature, many oceanic regions worldwide still need to be explored. In this study, we investigate the transport of plastic debris to the Gulf Coast beaches of the United States to identify the sources of microplastic in the region.

The Gulf of Mexico, also known as the Gulf of America (GoA), is the world's largest Gulf. It is connected to the Atlantic Ocean and the Caribbean Sea, with a surface area of 615,000 square miles, a width of 810 miles, and a maximum depth of 4,384 meters. The GoA is rich in natural resources: the coastal waters are full of seafood and shellfish, the offshore waters are an essential source for the fishing, oil, and natural gas industries, and the beautiful beaches attracting millions yearly provide an economic backbone for many coastal communities. The GoA is particularly subject to microplastic pollution because of the many plastic discharge locations by coastal regions through port areas, tourism activities, river systems, and industrial activities. It is also home to the most plastic manufacturers in the United States, predominately in and around Galveston Bay, Texas, with additional processing plants stretching through the beaches of Texas, Louisiana, and Florida (BeyondPlastics, 2021). Over 47% of the U.S. petroleum refining capacity is located along the Gulf and contains 51% of the U.S. natural gas processing plant capacity (U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2023). The presence of oil, natural gas, and plastic waste makes the GoA a primary ecotoxicological concern for potentially high concentrations of toxins entering the Gulf.

Due to the severity of the problem, many organizations have been developed to identify and minimize the impact of plastic debris in the GoA. The Gulf of Mexico Alliance (GOMA) is a regional ocean partnership focused on enhancing the environmental and economic health of the Gulf. GOMA's Marine Debris Cross-team Initiative's (MDCTI) goal is to assess, prevent, remove, and eliminate marine debris and litter in the GoA by supporting community science groups such as the EPA's Escaped Trash Assessment Protocol, the Marine Debris Tracker, the Nurdle Patrol, and NOAA's Marine Debris Monitoring and Assessment Project tool (Grace et al., 2022). Barring the Nurdle Patrol, most of these groups focus on large debris and do not directly assess microplastics. Still, their data and work have been essential to understanding plastic waste in the GoA.

In addition to these efforts, several studies have been conducted on microplastics in the

GoA. A recent survey by Shruti et al. (2021) studied the 14 research articles published on microplastics in the GoA. They concluded that extensive research is needed to determine the impacts of microplastics in the GoA due to non-standardized methodologies making it difficult to unify the work already done. Even with ongoing efforts, there is still a shortage of knowledge about the transport of microplastics in the GoA from source to sink. The research done to understand plastic in the GoA is unique because of the focus on beached microplastics. More specifically, the collection of surveys conducted by the Nurdle Patrol, the most extensive publicly available microplastic data, provides a spatiotemporal distribution of beached primary microplastic pellets. We propose to analyze this sink data to map beached microplastic in the GoA to its source, using a Bayesian framework in combination with Lagrangian backtracking simulations, expanding upon the approach presented in Van Duinen et al. (2022).

This article is organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the features of study region as well as the beaching data collected from Nurdle Patrol surveys in this region. A robust description of the Bayesian framework including the numerical technique for likelihood calculation is included in Section 3. Application of this method to the data from GoA is described in Section 4. Section 5 contains posterior inference on the spatial and temporal aspects of microplastic source attribution in GoA. Finally, in Section 6, we summarize the contribution of this article and identify important directions for future research.

2. Data Collection and Study Region

The Nurdle Patrol has been compiling surveys on beached primary microplastic pellets (nurdles) found in North America since 2018. Each survey records the date, location (latitude and longitude), and number of nurdles found. In this study, we consider 2,102 nurdle surveys conducted within the extended GoA region inside the rectangle $[97.98^{\circ}W, 76.46^{\circ}W] \times [18.14^{\circ}N, 31.9^{\circ}N]$ from July 2019 to December 2021. Throughout this article, we shall refer to this region as the GoA. Figure 1 displays a general-purpose domain map of this region.

Figure 1: A map of the Gulf of America (GoA). For a rigorous definition of each state, country, and oceanic region, see Figure 2. Note that some names therein are abbreviated for convenience.

The data is collected using citizen science, where volunteers survey beaches by handpicking nurdles. The survey is carried out in 10-minute intervals, where each interval is done at the following water line, starting at the current water line during low tide and ending at the vegetation line. Citizen scientists are encouraged to choose a beach or multiple beaches to

survey once a month, providing temporal sampling at regular intervals. Once the survey is complete, it is submitted to the Nurdle Patrol website and added to their database. The data is then standardized concerning the collection method and other factors that could artificially inflate the nurdle count. See Tunnell et al. (2020) for further details regarding this data or collection method. The datasets can be accessed on their website, see Appendix A.2.

This study region consists of important geographic and oceanographic divisions as displayed in the left and right panels, respectively, of Figure 2. In Section 5, we are going to explore microplastic beaching events and source attribution aggregated at the scale of these regions. We will refer to these two groups as the coastal and oceanic regions, respectively.

Figure 2: (left) Coastal labels are assigned by country or state in the domain. (right) Oceanic labels are assigned using Lagrangian dynamical geographic regions defined by Miron et al. (2017). These regions were chosen manually and not determined directly from their work.

For this article, we assume that the data provided by the Nurdle Patrol reasonably represents the spatiotemporal beaching pattern of all microplastic types of similar size and shape in the US Gulf Coast. The spatial distribution of the empirical beaching pattern, averaged over the study period, is displayed in Figure 3. The beaching data is preprocessed to keep the computational load feasible, see Section 4.2.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the number of nurdles collected within a 10-30 minute period at different coastal locations, between 2019-07-01 and 2021-12-31. The actual nurdle survey locations are binned to the closest coastal locations, see Section 4.1 for more details.

Finally, Figure 4 provides a comprehensive summary of the distributions of conducted surveys and collected nurdles across different calendar months and Gulf Coast states. Survey sites of beaching were located in Texas (81%), Louisiana (5%), Mississippi (9%), Alabama (2%), and Florida (3%). Since the study period is 1.5 years long, the months January to June

occur only once, and the months July to December occur twice. Hence, the members of latter group are expected to have taller bars in the panels representing monthwise counts for surveys or nurdles. Surveys have been conducted at higher rates in Texas throughout the year, potentially due the Nurdle Patrol’s project origin at Harte Research Institute at Texas A&M University–Corpus Christi. However, higher survey rates do not necessarily imply higher nurdle counts. For the months of August and October, Texas had a decrease in the number of nurdles found, whereas Mississippi saw a significant increase in the number of nurdles given relatively low survey rates. Another example is the comparison between Louisiana and Mississippi. In April, they had an equal number of surveys (= 11) but more nurdles were collected in Mississippi. Going to August, again they have an equal (but larger) number of surveys (= 18) but Mississippi actually decreased nurdle counts from April while Louisiana saw the huge increase in nurdle counts. Therefore, the number of nurdles do not show any systematic pattern of dependence on the number of surveys.

Furthermore, we examined nurdle collection rate per survey as a function of month, shown in the bottom right panel of Figure 4. We glean that the highest density of nurdles found for a given survey are collected in Louisiana during the Fall and Winter months with an additional peak in February, suggesting seasonal periods of higher plastic debris. In Texas, we see clear seasonality in plastic debris with higher nurdle density in the Spring and Summer months and lower counts during Fall and Winter, agreeing with the peak accumulation seasons identified by Wessel et al. (2019). Overall, the dominance of nurdles found on Texas coastlines and density found in Louisiana indicate that these regions are major sinks for plastic debris (Grace et al., 2022; Tunnell et al., 2020; Wessel et al., 2019).

Figure 4: Important summary statistics from Nurdle Patrol Surveys conducted between 2019-07-01 and 2021-12-31 (Tunnell et al., 2020): (top left) State-wise numbers and proportions of surveys conducted and nurdles collected, (top right) Month- and State-wise distribution of number of surveys, (bottom left) Month- and State-wise distribution of collected nurdles, (bottom right) Month- and State-wise distribution of nurdle collection rate per survey.

3. Methods

Let \mathcal{A} denote the spatial domain and $\mathcal{W} = [t_L, t_R]$ denote the time interval for this study. Let ξ denote a generic microplastic, also referred to as a particle, that gets released in the ocean at time t_o and returns to the beach at time t_b . We shall refer to t_o and t_b as the source and beaching times, respectively. We assume a microplastic can float in the ocean for a maximum time length ν , so $t_b - \nu < t_o < t_b$. For this article, we only consider microplastics that beached in \mathcal{A} during \mathcal{W} , which implies $t_b \in \mathcal{W}$ and $t_o \in \tilde{\mathcal{W}} = [t_L - \nu, t_L] \cup \mathcal{W}$. Let $X(t)$ be the function that represents location of ξ at any time $t \in [t_o, t_b]$. Hence, $X(t_o)$ represents the location where ξ got released in the ocean and $X(t_b)$ represents the location where it was beached. We shall refer to $X(t_o)$ and $X(t_b)$ as source and beaching locations, respectively. The set $\{(t, X(t)) : t_o \leq t \leq t_b\}$ represents the entire spatiotemporal trajectory of ξ in the ocean. For this study, we assume that the spatial trajectory of ξ lies entirely inside \mathcal{A} .

Our dataset consists of information on where and when a collection of n particles, denoted by $\Xi_n = \{\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n\}$, were found on the beach across all surveys. To denote their individual beaching locations and times, we append a particle-specific subscript to the notations introduced in the previous paragraph. So, we can represent the available information on beaching events as $\{(t_{i,b}, X(t_{i,b})) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$. The interest lies in inferring about unknown source locations and times for these particles that can be similarly represented as $\{(t_{i,o}, X(t_{i,o})) : i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

We introduce partitions for \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{W} into disjoint bins $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_S\}$ and $\{W_0, W_1, W_2, \dots, W_T\}$, respectively. We refer to the spatial bins as *gridcells* and temporal bins as *windows*. If we assume d additional windows are needed to cover the time span $[t_L - \nu, t_L)$, the augmented collection $\{W_{-d}, W_{-d+1}, \dots, W_{-1}, W_0, W_1, \dots, W_T\}$ represents the corresponding partition of $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$. All subsequent probability computations are done at the level of these bins. Hence, if we want to infer about source time $t_{i,o}$ and location $X(t_{i,o})$ for the i -th particle ξ_i , it will be in terms of which window and gridcell they lie inside. In a Bayesian paradigm, the answer will be expressed in the form of a discrete posterior probability distribution over members of $\{A_s : 1 \leq s \leq S\} \times \{W_\eta : -d \leq \eta \leq T\}$. In Section 3.4, we provide reasons behind carrying out inference at the bin-level which is a common practice in ocean microplastic modeling literature (Pierard et al., 2022; Van Duinen et al., 2022; Van Sebille et al., 2018). We develop this approach below.

It follows from Bayes theorem that,

$$\text{Posterior} \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Source} \\ \text{Event} \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{c} \text{Beaching} \\ \text{Data} \end{array} \right) \propto \text{Likelihood} \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Beaching} \\ \text{Data} \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{c} \text{Source} \\ \text{Event} \end{array} \right) \times \text{Prior} \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Source} \\ \text{Event} \end{array} \right).$$

Using available data on the beaching time $t_{i,b}$ and location $X(t_{i,b})$ for the particle ξ_i , we easily determine the window and gridcell for its beaching event and, denote them as $W_{\eta'(i)}$ and $A_{s'(i)}$, respectively. We use Bayes theorem to stochastically connect the bins for its source and beaching events as:

$$\begin{aligned} & P(\xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta \mid \xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)}) \\ &= P(\xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)} \mid \xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta) \times \\ & \quad \frac{P(\xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta)}{P(\xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)})}, \quad 1 \leq s \leq S, \quad -d \leq \eta \leq T \quad (3.1) \end{aligned}$$

where the expression in the left hand side represents the joint posterior probability mass for the particle's source location and time being in bins A_s and W_η , respectively, given the gridcell and window for its beaching location and time. Clearly, this probability would be

nonzero only if W_η is at most d bins to the left of $W_{\eta'(i)}$. The first term in the right hand side is the bin-level likelihood of available beaching data for ξ_i assuming the bins for its source location and time. This quantity is estimated using Lagrangian backtracking simulations discussed in Section 3.1. The numerator in the second term, $P(\xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta)$, is the prior probability mass for the source location and time being in bins A_s and W_η , respectively. Our interpretation of this quantity is described in Section 3.2. The denominator is the marginal probability, for the observed beaching window and gridcell for ξ_i no matter where and when it has been released in the ocean. It is the normalizing constant for the posterior distribution that is discussed in Section 3.3.

3.1 Likelihood Calculation Using Lagrangian Framework

To calculate the bin-level likelihood in Equation (3.1), we employ a Lagrangian ocean analysis framework using OceanParcels (Delandmeter and Sebille, 2019; Lange and Van Sebille, 2017) to backtrack a particle’s trajectory in time. We follow the framework presented by Van Sebille et al. (2018) and Van Duinen et al. (2022) to provide an overview of the simulation tool.

The Lagrangian kinematic approach represents particles floating in the open ocean in a fluid reference frame where particles are defined as infinitesimal small fluid particles called fluid parcels. The continuous accumulation of these fluid parcels describes fluid motion. The Lagrangian approach leverages fluid descriptions (i.e., velocity fields) from Eulerian kinematics, which describes fluid motion in a reference frame fixed in space, to estimate the trajectories of virtual fluid particles. The OceanParcels simulator allows us to represent microplastics as virtual particles advected by velocity field data. The location $X(t)$ of a particle at time t is updated by time stepping the surface flow velocity $\vec{v}(X(t), t)$ as:

$$X(t - \Delta t) = X(t) - \int_{t-\Delta t}^t \vec{v}(X(\tau), \tau) d\tau + R\sqrt{2K\Delta t}, \quad (3.2)$$

where a stochastic noise term is added to represent the effects of horizontal diffusion on sub-scale grid eddies. This term includes (i) $R \sim N(0, 1)$, (ii) the integration time step Δt chosen by user, and (iii) the eddy diffusivity K . In Section 4.1, we discuss how $\vec{v}(X(t), t)$ is calculated for the current application using data on local ocean characteristics. Value of K is determined locally using the Smagorinsky method (Smagorinsky, 1963) as:

$$K = C_s \Delta x \Delta y \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}\right)^2}, \quad (3.3)$$

where $0 < C_s < 1$ is the Smagorinsky constant, a dimensionless tuning parameter chosen by the user that determines the size of the sub-scale grid eddy bounded by the cell area $\Delta x \Delta y$. The velocity gradients under the square root term are derived from Eulerian ocean velocity field data where the components of the velocities $\vec{v}(X(t), t)$ are split into their eastward (u) and northward (v) velocities and calculated with respect to their x and y coordinates. For additional information about the interpretation and computation of the Smagorinsky method, see Van Sebille et al. (2018) and the OceanParcels documentation webpage in Appendix A.2.

For each particle in Ξ_n , we release one *virtual particle* exactly at the beaching time and location of that particle and simulate its trajectory backwards in time using Equation (3.2). Hence, for the virtual particle corresponding to ξ_i , the simulation starts at time $t_{i,b}$ and location $X(t_{i,b})$. Since we have assumed that a particle can not float in the ocean beyond a time span ν , this backtracking simulation runs up to time $t_{i,b} - \nu$. Every trajectory

constructed in this way is essentially a sequence of location-time pairs where two successive time points are Δt apart. Once trajectories for all virtual particles are simulated backwards in time as above, we use them to calculate the likelihood, at the bin-level, as outlined below.

Consider all virtual particles that are released inside a gridcell $A_{s'}$ within a window $W_{\eta'}$. As we previously assumed that d windows are needed to cover a time span of length ν , their trajectories go up to d windows preceding the initial window $W_{\eta'}$. Now we find the gridcells these trajectories pass through only during the first window (i.e., the beaching window $W_{\eta'}$). For each $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, S\}$, we count the number of location-time pairs from these trajectories that lie inside A_s during $W_{\eta'}$ and denote it using $N_{s', \eta'}(s, \eta')$. Hence, the longer a trajectory spends inside a specific gridcell (during that window), it contributes more location-time pairs there, pushing the corresponding count higher. We repeat this counting step separately for each of the d preceding time windows $W_{\eta'-1}, W_{\eta'-2}, \dots, W_{\eta'-d}$. Consequently, we obtain a set of counts $\mathcal{N}_{s', \eta'} = \{N_{s', \eta'}(s, \eta) : 1 \leq s \leq S, \eta' - d \leq \eta \leq \eta'\}$ where $N_{s', \eta'}(s, \eta)$ represents the number of location-time pairs inside $A_s \times W_\eta$ from the trajectories of all virtual particles released in $A_{s'} \times W_{\eta'}$.

Next, we shift to another spatiotemporal bin (by changing s' or η' or both), consider virtual particles released inside that bin, and repeat the above steps of computation. We keep doing this until we cover all virtual particles released in $\mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{W}$ to obtain the superset of counts $\cup_{s'=1}^S \cup_{\eta'=1}^T \mathcal{N}_{s', \eta'}$. Regrouping these counts according to unique (s, η) pairs, we can view them as observations from multinomial distributions depending on source bins. Hence, the maximum likelihood estimate of the bin-wise probability for the beaching events given the source bin can be computed using the corresponding sample proportion as:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\text{Beaching Event in } A_{s'} \times W_{\eta'} \mid \text{Source Event in } A_s \times W_\eta) \\ = N_{s', \eta'}(s, \eta) \bigg/ \sum_{a=1}^S \sum_{b=\eta}^{\eta+d} N_{a, b}(s, \eta). \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Setting $\eta' = \eta'(i)$ and $s' = s'(i)$ in above equation gives us the bin-level likelihood for the beaching data of particle ξ_i that appears in Equation (3.1). See Figure A.1 of the Supplementary Information for a visual illustration of likelihood computation.

3.2 Prior Specification

The prior probability mass $P(\xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta)$, mentioned in Equation (3.1), is assigned based on the knowledge about possible microplastic origin locations for every gridcell in \mathcal{A} at different time windows within \mathcal{W} . This can be done utilizing available data on the different sources that contribute microplastics to the ocean (Kaandorp et al., 2020; Van Duinen et al., 2022) such as plastic waste generated in land near coastal areas, plastic carried by the rivers that run into the ocean and human activities in the ocean including shipping, fishing and aquaculture. In this article, we consider three source types: land (L), river (R), and fishing activity (F) so that, for any generic particle ξ ,

$$P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta) := \pi_L(s, \eta) + \pi_R(s, \eta) + \pi_F(s, \eta). \quad (3.5)$$

The quantities in the right-hand side can be interpreted as follows. Out of all microplastics that got released in the ocean within \mathcal{A} during \mathcal{W} from all source types, $\pi_L(s, \eta)$ is the a priori fraction that got released in gridcell A_s during the window W_η from land. Similar interpretation follows for each of $\pi_R(s, \eta)$ and $\pi_F(s, \eta)$ with change in source type. One can marginalize these quantities in different ways (across gridcells, windows) to compute prior probabilities that show how the relative prevalence of three source types varies across seasons

or by geography. For example, to learn a priori contribution of a source type $B \in \{L, R, F\}$ in the microplastic beached somewhere in \mathcal{A} anytime during \mathcal{W} , one can compute

$$P(\xi \text{ has Source type } B) = \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{\eta=-d}^T \pi_B(s, \eta). \quad (3.6)$$

In Section 4.2, we discuss how the prior mass is assigned across gridcells, windows and source types for the current application.

3.3 Posterior Inference

The remaining term in the formula for the posterior probability in Equation (3.1) is the denominator which represents its normalizing constant and can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & P(\xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)}) \\ &= \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{\eta=\eta'(i)-d}^{\eta'(i)} P(\xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)} \mid \xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta) \\ & \quad \times P(\xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta), \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

where the first term inside the summation is the bin-level likelihood calculated using Equation (3.4) and the second term is the prior probability given by Equation (3.5).

It may be of interest to compute posterior probabilities for the three source types discussed in Section (3.2). For example, we may want to compute the posterior probability for ξ_i being released in the Ocean from a land source. Note that since the numerical simulation that determines the likelihood of beaching events is invariant to the source type, only the prior terms need modification. In general, for any source type $B \in \{L, R, F\}$, we can compute

$$\begin{aligned} & P(\xi_i \text{ has Source type } B \mid \xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)}) \\ &= \frac{1}{C} \times \sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{\eta=\eta'(i)-d}^{\eta'(i)} P(\xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)} \mid \xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta) \\ & \quad \times \pi_B(s, \eta), \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where C is the normalizing constant from Equation (3.7).

If our interest lies in the source event for any generic microplastic ξ (that is beached somewhere in \mathcal{A} anytime during \mathcal{W}), that can be computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} & P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta \mid \Xi_n) \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n P(\xi_i \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta \mid \xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

This expression is the weighted average of probabilities from Equation (3.1) with weights determined by empirical distribution of beached particles. Since the likelihood and prior probabilities are determined at bin levels (gridcell and window), this particle-wise sum can also be grouped according to how many particles were beached at any gridcell-window combination. Note that the terms inside the above summation will be positive only for particles with beaching window index $\in \{\eta, \eta + 1, \dots, \eta + d\}$.

Inference focussing solely on source location for ξ requires marginalizing Equation (3.9) over

all possible source windows as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s | \Xi_n) &= P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s \times \mathcal{W} | \Xi_n) \\
 &= \sum_{\eta=-d}^T P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s \times W_\eta | \Xi_n).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.10}$$

Note that $P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s)$ and $P(\xi \text{ sourced in } A_s | \Xi_n)$ represent gridcell-specific prior and posterior probabilities for source locations of the beached microplastic particles. Their comparison will be useful to understand what role the observed dataset plays, relative to the prior distribution, in determining where the microplastic particles found at the beach are likely released in the ocean. For the current application, we present this analysis in Section 5.

In addition to location and time for the source event, one may want to learn what fraction of microplastics, that got beached somewhere in \mathcal{A} anytime during \mathcal{W} , was from a source type $B \in \{L, R, F\}$. That probability can be computed using

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P(\xi \text{ has Source type B} | \Xi_n) \\
 &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n P(\xi_i \text{ has Source type B} | \xi_i \text{ beached in } A_{s'(i)} \times W_{\eta'(i)}).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.11}$$

Similar to our discussion after Equation (3.9), this represents a weighted sum of probabilities from Equation (3.8) with weights determined by empirical distribution of beached particles and can be grouped based on fraction of particles beached at every gridcell-window combination. It represents posterior contribution from a specific source type and can be compared against the corresponding prior contribution (Equation (3.6)). For the current application, this comparison is shown in Table 1 of Section 5.

3.4 Additional Discussion

Let us explain why we define bins across space and time and develop the likelihood, prior, and posterior distributions involving source and beaching event probabilities at the bin-level. Using Equations (3.2) and (3.3) in likelihood calculation requires the surface flow velocity $\vec{v}(X(t), t)$ which is available, *not* at every point location in the ocean at every instant, but only at a bin-level both spatially and temporally. The trajectories generated using numerical integration contain locations only at time points that are Δt apart, so it is impossible to know the position of any virtual particle on a continuous timescale. In this section, we have described the equations and distributions in general terms so that one can work with bins at any chosen spatiotemporal resolution. It should be remembered that working at finer resolutions (such as choosing a smaller value for time step Δt in numerical simulation) comes at the expense of higher computational costs.

One may also be interested spatial and/or temporal aggregation of the bin-level posterior inference for source and beaching events. Here, instead of considering a single gridcell (window) for the source/beaching location (time) of a particle, we consider a group of adjacent gridcells (windows) for such events and compute posterior probabilities at that aggregated scale. Figure 2 displays the coastal and oceanic regions as candidates for spatial aggregation. Temporal aggregation may be based on calendar months or calendar years. Since the posterior distribution treats the source location and/or time as random conditional on beaching location and/or time, any aggregation with respect to source gridcells/windows requires a simple sum of bin-level posterior source probabilities for those gridcells/windows. On the other hand, any aggregation with respect to beaching gridcells/windows must be

done by first calculating posterior probabilities conditional on bin-level beaching information and subsequently combining them using weights determined from the empirical distribution of beached particles at those gridcells/windows. In Section 5, we discuss posterior inference at such aggregated space and time scales for the current application.

We conclude this section by noting that although our approach uses a Bayesian framework similar to that of Van Duinen et al. (2022), there exist key differences between the two. The most important one is how posterior normalizing constant (the denominator in Equation (3.1)) is calculated. Here, we compute it in the conventional way, in Equation (3.7), by combining the likelihood and prior over all possible bin choices for the source event. On the other hand, the aforementioned article computes the normalizing constant so that the posterior probability of any source type becomes a pre-specified known value. Consequently, the resulting posterior calculations may differ drastically between the two approaches. In our approach, posterior probability of any source type, as determined in Equation (3.11), is data-dependent and does not necessarily match the prior probability for the same whereas, in their approach, it is known beforehand. Second, as far as posterior inference at an aggregated spatial or temporal scale is concerned, Van Duinen et al. (2022) assumed a constant flux of beached particles which implies bin-level posterior probabilities for different beaching gridcells/windows can always be aggregated with uniform weights. On the other hand, our dataset has variable rate of beaching events at different spatiotemporal bins and, as the preceding paragraph discusses, any aggregation must use weights based on empirical distribution of beached particles at constituent gridcells/windows. Third, throughout our model development and use of notations, we have rigorously distinguished between quantities that correspond to information at the point-level vs. bin-level. For example, although the likelihood and prior probabilities are modeled at the bin-level, the numerical simulation of virtual particle trajectories are based on point-level locations and times. Fourth, for the Lagrangian simulation, Van Duinen et al. (2022) use a uniform diffusivity constant K in Equation (3.2) whereas we determine K locally using Equation (3.3). To run the simulations, we have utilized a higher resolution velocity field, see Section 4.1.

4. Model Implementation

Whereas Section 3 described the Bayesian framework in generic terms, the specifics of how to use it with the Nurdle Patrol data from GoA is discussed below. We begin with details of numerical simulations necessary for likelihood computation, followed by elicitation of the prior distribution for microplastic source in GoA.

4.1 Numerical Simulation and Likelihood Computation

As described in Section 3.1, we compute the likelihood by performing a backward-in-time Lagrangian simulation using OceanParcels in which we release virtual particles from beached nurdle locations and tracked them through the GoA surface flow. Virtual particles are released daily between July 2019 and December 2021, equal to the number of observed nurdles at the corresponding bins, for a total of 349,177 particles. Every virtual particle is backtracked for a maximum of 6 months from its release. Their trajectories are integrated in Equation (3.2) using a 4th-order Runge-Kutta scheme with a time step of 2 hours. This simulation exercise was implemented in Python (version 3.9) using a single Xeon Gold 6126 processor and 192 GB RAM with a maximum runtime of thirteen hours.

In the open ocean, buoyant microplastics are transported by surface currents, Stokes drift, and vertical mixing with subsurface currents (Van Sebille et al., 2020). All three processes

are essential for describing microplastic dispersion. However, we exclude the vertical mixing of microplastics in the water column as it is an ongoing research topic, and its effects on the particles in the ocean are relatively unknown (Choy et al., 2019; Fischer et al., 2022). Also, including a 3D simulation would drastically increase the computation and the model complexity. Therefore, particles are advected using a summed velocity field of the surface current + Stokes drift, a similar forcing scenario to Van Duinen et al. (2022) representing microplastic trajectories that float on or just below the surface of the water column. We use the HYCOM + NCODA Gulf of Mexico $1/25^\circ$ Analysis data (Metzger et al., 2014) for hourly surface currents and $1/5^\circ$ Global Wave Reanalysis WAVERYS data (Copernicus Marine Service Information, E.U., 2021) for three-hourly Stokes drift. In Equation (3.2), after integrating the trajectories, we account for unresolved turbulence acting on floating microplastics by adding the horizontal diffusivity using the Smagorinsky method. We chose $C_s = 0.1$ in Equation (3.3), same as what is used in the OceanParcels (see the link for documentation webpage in Appendix A.2).

To release particles in the GoA, we use the Parcels framework to define the $1/25^\circ \times 1/25^\circ$ 2D Arakawa A-grid spanning the spatial domain. The gridcells are labeled as land, coast, or ocean based on the HYCOM surface current data at the vertices (often called nodes). This scheme allows us to distinguish the particle’s location to determine where the particles are released and their interaction with the land-ocean boundary. Cells with surface velocities of zero magnitude at all nodes are considered land and are outside the domain. Cells that border at least one land cell are considered the coast, and cells that border no land cells are considered the ocean. See Figure 5 for an illustrative example. We define the domain for potential source gridcells only using the coast and ocean cells visited by the virtual particles at least once during the backtracking simulation, implying that we only consider cells that contribute non-zero likelihood values for beaching events. Once these labels are data-mined from the simulation trajectories, there are a total of 114,024 source cells with 2,677 labeled coastal cells and 111,347 labeled ocean cells.

Figure 5: The image represents an Arakawa A-grid where each node (vertex) contains information about the velocity components for an example HYCOM hindcast surface current vector field for the Mississippi Delta region on December 31st, 2019. As illustrated here for a subset of the domain, this structure is used to define the land, coastal, and ocean cells over the entire GoA region.

As mentioned in Section 3.1, each virtual particle released into the domain represents an individual murdle. One-to-one representation often comes with a computational cost, but here,

we preprocess the data accordingly. First, we limit the maximum number of nurdles counted from a single survey to 10,000, ensuring extreme values don't bias the model. In our case, there were only 11 surveys ($< 0.5\%$ of all surveys) that recorded more than 10,000 nurdles, with two of those surveys reporting 500,000 nurdles. We found that limiting the maximum nurdle count led to an average of 180 particles released daily, consistent with previous ocean microplastic modeling studies (Pierard et al., 2022; Van Duinen et al., 2022). Second, we reposition the raw nurdle locations for all surveys by placing them randomly inside the nearest coastal cell. The dataset also includes some locations on the land significantly away from the coastline. To ensure that the release locations reflect realistic beaching sites, we only consider nurdles surveys completed within 50 km of the coastal line. Lastly, once the virtual particles are assigned, they are released at the corresponding time and location within a coastal cell.

Microplastics floating in the ocean can be lost due to sinking and beaching, driven by complex physical and biological processes. The sinking of microplastic can happen through degradation or biofouling, often modeled as decay in the mass represented by the particle (Fischer et al., 2022). We exclude these processes since we do not have data on sunk plastic in the GoA. The beaching of microplastic is difficult to model in great detail, and key mechanisms are yet to be discovered (Van Sebille et al., 2018). So they are either modeled stochastically (Onink et al., 2022) or directly by removing particles that are pushed onto land. However, since particles have already beached from where they are released for backtracking, the simulation does not implement explicit beaching processes. Therefore, particles in our simulation either stay within the domain for their entire lifespan or exit the domain prematurely to the surrounding oceans.

To prevent virtual particles from getting stuck on land through interpolation errors, we take the approach used by Van Duinen et al. (2022) and Delandmeter and Sebille (2019) by pushing particles away from the boundaries when they end up on land through the following procedure. We first update the particle's location following the surface current advection. Then, we check whether the particle's location is more than 5 km ($\approx 1/50^\circ$ or half of the cell length) from land. If not, the particle is displaced away from the land cell according to the local normal vector at the boundary. Then, the particle is moved according to its local Stokes drift and diffusion. If the particle moves onto land during this step, the trajectory is prevented from doing so by freezing it in place for the remainder of the backtracking windows. This ensures that all particles stay within domain cells. Once the particles are tracked for 6 months, they are removed from the simulation.

Furthermore, if a particle exits the domain during the simulation, we stop tracking it and exclude it from further consideration. In that case, we only record the part of its trajectory that stays within the domain boundaries. After running the simulation, we found that a total of 9.96% of the particles left the domain either to the Atlantic Ocean or the Caribbean Sea. Exiting trajectories are neglected for several reasons. In the prior, it is unlikely for both out-of-bounds regions to be sources of plastic (see Figure 6). Since the Atlantic Ocean is outside the GoA domain, we do not consider plastic entering from the open ocean. For the Caribbean Sea, a study by Courtene-Jones et al. (2021) found that the area is susceptible to plastic pollution from surrounding regions, mainly from Latin and South America, indicating that the region is a potential sink, not a source of plastic pollution.

To calculate the likelihood, we bin the points on the trajectories using the $1/25^\circ \times 1/25^\circ$ resolution spatial grid at a monthly temporal scale. As indicated in Section 3.4, our methodology can be applied at any discrete spatiotemporal resolution. Compared to the studies included in existing literature, we have used the highest spatial resolution with the largest temporal domain from the most up-to-date available data. Given the temporal domain of 3 years, we found that assigning gridcells at the $1/25^\circ \times 1/25^\circ$ spatial resolution for monthly temporal windows yielded the most explicable results. To illustrate the likelihood

computation within the Bayesian framework, we provide an example in Appendix A.1 using a subset of the actual simulated trajectories.

4.2 Prior Information and Source Determination

To determine the prior from Equation (3.5), we utilized globally modeled month-wise estimates for all plastic input into the ocean based on the source types, similar to the approach in Van Duinen et al. (2022) and Kaandorp et al. (2020). However, since plastics of greater size are not considered in our model, the plastic input estimates are assumed to be proportional to microplastic input. We recognize that this may not be the most informative prior. However, research agrees that larger plastic and microplastic transport methods from each source type to the ocean are similar (Kaandorp et al., 2020; Van Sebille et al., 2020). Multiple studies recognize that global estimates of microplastic input into the ocean may be underestimated (Boucher and Friot, 2017; Eriksen et al., 2014; Van Sebille et al., 2015). After all, if more precise information is collected on microplastic input sources, our prior distribution can be updated accordingly. Each of the data sources is described below.

Plastic entering the GoA from land sources (L) is derived from the amount of mismanaged plastic waste (MPW) generated within 50 km of the coast (Jambeck et al., 2015) that enters the ocean. Land inputs are specified from a study by Lebreton and Andrady (2019), who used national plastic waste generation data, population size, and GDP to generate a high-resolution (30 x 30 arc second, 1km) map of global MPW for 2019. We assume, for the duration of this study, that the plastic input from land sources remains constant over time.

Plastic entering the GoA from river sources (R) is derived from direct MPW emissions transported from rivers to the ocean. River inputs are specified from another study by Lebreton et al. (2017), where they used national plastic waste generation data, population size, and watershed area to generate an average mass of plastic exiting the mouth of 40,760 rivers worldwide. Again, since this data is aggregated per year, we assume that the plastic input from river sources remains constant over time for the duration of this study.

Plastic entering the GoA from fishing (F) is defined as plastic entering the ocean from fishing activities. This data comes from the Global Fishing Watch map (Park et al., 2023), which estimates these quantities using satellite technology and machine learning to track and record the fishing and shipping vessels worldwide. We assume that higher fishing activities correspond with higher plastic inputs and vice versa. This data is taken daily from available Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ) in the GoA. However, due to the high computational cost, we average the marine activity density per month and calculate the time-varying prior $\pi_F(s, \eta)$ to match the simulation period.

Since the Global Fishing Watch map does not report MPW emissions, we utilize globally estimated proportions of MPW based on source type to calculate its MPW contribution. We recognize that these quantities should reflect the regional proportions of microplastic sources in the GoA. According to Shruti et al. (2021), the key drivers of microplastic input to the GoA were land-based and ocean-based sources (coastal, river, and marine activities). However, the contribution of each non-point source has not yet been established for the GoA. Since the proportion for each source type $\{L, R, F\}$ is unknown, we use global estimates computed by Lebreton et al. (2018) as a baseline to analyze source attribution. Their global estimates claim that 59.8% of plastic originates from coastal populations, 12.1% from riverine sources, 17.9% from fisheries, 8.9% from shipping, and 1.3% from aquaculture. We exclude shipping and aquaculture due to the lack of public data on these quantities and renormalize the total contribution from other three sources. Therefore, we assume that, a priori, 66.6% of plastic originates from coastal populations (L), 13.4% from river sources (R), and 20%

from fishing activities (F). Once again, if GoA-specific numbers are available, the prior can be accordingly updated.

To compute the prior for each source, we first assign each MPW count from the corresponding dataset to its spatiotemporal bin using a 2D histogram. For land sources, we degrade the map’s resolution and sum the non-zero MPW counts from land cells to the nearest coastal cell. For river sources, we reposition the recorded latitude and longitude for the mouth of the river to the center of the closest coastal cell. For fishing activity, we calculate the MPW contribution based on the global proportion and degrade the resolution of the spatiotemporal distribution to match the resolution used in the likelihood calculation. We compute the prior probabilities for each source type as described in Section 3.2. Figure 6 shows the relative mass contributions associated with each source type.

Figure 6: MPW mass contributions of monthly average fishing, land, and river sources between 2019 and 2021. These values were used to construct the prior probability distribution. River sources that contributed less than 10 kg/month were excluded so as not to overcrowd the graph.

5. Posterior Inference on Source Attribution

A general overview of the posterior microplastic source distribution, aggregated over the study duration, is shown in Figure 7. We find significant changes in the posterior spatial pattern for source locations compared to Figure 6 which showed a priori source locations. In the prior, microplastic sources are attributed to large coastal populations and coastlines in high tourism areas likely identified by the high risk of reported MPW. In the posterior, the main source clusters agree with estimates of previous microplastic studies in the region as summarized by Shruti et al. (2021), and are driven by the Loop Current and strong westward surface currents. The highest-density regions along these coastlines are centered around New Orleans, Galveston Bay, Corpus Christi, and Mérida. This suggests that microplastic pollution can be attributed to the large tourism destinations along the GoA coastlines. The regions along the US coastline also correlate with the locations of nurdle pellet factories shown in BeyondPlastics (2021, Appendix 5) report. Although pellet factory locations were not explicitly taken into consideration while constructing the prior distribution in Section 4.2, these locations are typically centered near larger cities with a higher risk of MPW used

Figure 7: Map of gridcell-wise posterior source probabilities for particles from fishing, land, and river sources, aggregated over the duration of study (2019-2021). River sources that contributed less than 0.001% were excluded so as not to overcrowd the graph.

in the prior. The Caribbean has been identified as the possible source region, as was also seen in prior. This suggests that regions southeast of the GoA may impact the amount of microplastic beaching on northern coastlines, further supporting a positive association between a source location and tourist destination.

In Table 1, we present how overall contributions from different source types are updated in the posterior from their prior values. The regional fishing source proportions doubled from the prior estimates. The posterior suggests that fishing operations closest to shore on the nWFS side of the Mississippi Delta region may attribute more microplastic pollution than other regions. It is clear that fishing activities near the coastlines can greatly impact the amount of microplastics beaching on the Texas and Louisiana coastlines. On the other hand, river sources nearly halved and were mostly attributed to the Grijalva River near Frontera, the Pearl River near New Orleans, and the rivers that exit into Galveston Bay. We note that the Grijalva River has a 3.2% probability of being the source of microplastic for beaches where nurdles were found (see Figure 3). We note that, in the prior distribution, there is strong contribution for river input from the Grijalva River, which matches the results shown in the River Plastic Pollution Map created by the Ocean Clean Up (see Appendix A.2) for the Grijalva River. We recognize that the model did not predict significant source attribution to the Mississippi River watershed discharge contrary to findings from several authors (Mauro et al., 2017; Shruti et al., 2021; Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2021; Wessel et al., 2019) on significant microplastic presence in the area. This discrepancy potentially comes from the averaging done on a global scale for the river MPW input data provided by Lebreton et al. (2017) that does not necessarily match the regional studies. Therefore, more localized information could be used to inform the prior distribution about the amount of microplastic discharged from the Mississippi River.

We explore how probabilities of different source regions vary as a function of calendar month of the beaching event and display the values in Figure 8. Strong seasonal variation is

Table 1: Prior and posterior microplastic contributions by source types

Source type	Land River Fishing activities		
Prior contribution (%)	66.6	13.4	20
Posterior contribution (%)	52.3	7.2	40.5

clear, and source probabilities follow the general pattern of microplastics being attributed to southern rivers and coastlines during the Summer months, while microplastic source contributions from the northern coasts, rivers, and fisheries are strongest the rest of the year. The spike in source probabilities during the Summer is attributed to coastlines and rivers in Mexico, which coincides with peak tourist seasons. Fishing sources in the LaTex and nWFS shelf regions peak in the months of May and November. This can be explained by the temporal variability in the prior $\pi_F(s, \eta)$, matching the peak fishing activity in the region (see the Global Fishing Watch Map in Appendix A.2).

Figure 8: Posterior source probabilities for different coastal and Gulf regions as function of beaching months of the year. Note that source probabilities for some Gulf regions may be too small to be visible.

5.1 Regional Particle Crossings

From the posterior distributions of beached nurdles, one can infer on the likely transport crossings, i.e., chance of microplastic traveling between source and beaching regions. We use the regions defined in Figure 2 to display probabilities for such inter- and intra- regional transport in Figure 9. We find that, for any beaching region, the coastal region with highest source probability is usually the beaching region itself (except Texas, which had the highest source probability from Mexico), and the oceanic region with highest source probability usually borders the beaching region. This is consistent with the results of multiple ocean current and tracer studies and microplastic surveys done in the region (Gough et al., 2019; Miron et al., 2017; Shruti et al., 2021; Wessel et al., 2019).

The regional oceanic geography is a driving factor for beaching locations in the GoA. We see this in Figure 3 where higher densities of nurdle beaching sites are found on the western Gulf coast. This beaching distribution matches the regions of attraction found by Miron et al. (2017) and can be explained by the Lagrangian dynamical geography. These spatial patterns

Figure 9: Posterior source probabilities for different coastal and Gulf regions as function of assigned nurdles coastal beaching regions. Note that this represents the crossing matrix for regions with the most significant source contributions.

can also be explained by the large seasonal loop current responsible for many oceanic events in the GoA, most notably contributing to the intensity of hurricanes during the summer. When the Loop Current is fully extended (see left panel in Figure 10) it will eventually shed a large eddy which drifts westwards (see right panel in Figure 10) while the Loop Current retracts to the south (NOAA, 2019). Combining this with the strong seasonal westward winds and surface currents, microplastic dispersion can stay regionally locked in the northern shelves and is less likely to be dispersed to other regions in the GoA. This is even less likely given that microplastics are often found near sources.

Figure 10: (left) Loop Current visible from Sea Surface Temperature observed by satellite (source: NOAA/AOML OceanViewer). (right) Track of Hurricane Katrina (2005) overlaid on top Tropical Cyclone Heat Potential (TCHP) condition on August 20, 2005. TCHP is the quantity of heat available in the ocean’s upper layer. Both images are sourced from NOAA (2019).

For the GoA, we find a 33% possible source contribution of microplastics from Mexico beaching on Texas coasts. A Lagrangian transport study by Gough et al. (2019) was done for the LaTex shelf region and found that particles sourced from Texas had a 19% chance of breaking from the shelf after 28 days, and particles sourced from further south had the same chance of breaking into shelf after 28 days. This supports our results given for the Texas coastline and LaTex shelf region since the majority of all particles released for backtracking

originated along this coastline, providing evidence for these escape events. Therefore, it is possible for particles to escape their regional shelf and disperse across the Gulf.

6. Discussion

In this article, we propose a probabilistic method for microplastic source attribution in the GoA using data on nurdle beaching events. Treating the nurdle source locations and times as unknown parameters, we use a Bayesian framework to infer about them from posterior distributions. Inference related to behavior of a generic microplastic particle can subsequently be drawn by weighted aggregation of nurdle-specific posterior probabilities based on empirical beaching distribution. This study uses input from real microplastic beaching data in a region that has not yet been studied to this degree. Our application creates a spatial map of dominant microplastic source regions for the years between 2019 and 2021. Our results show that microplastic sources in the GoA can be attributed to direct land input, fishing, and major rivers. We identified that the most likely river sources in the GoA were attributed to microplastic inputs from the Grijalva and Pearl Rivers during the Summer. Land sources had higher probabilities near larger cities and tourist destinations, with the most likely locations being New Orleans, Galveston Bay, Corpus Christi, and Mérida. Fishing activities were stronger around the Mississippi River Delta with clear temporal patterns. Overall, our results match the predictions made by Shruti et al. (2021) and could be used for upstream prevention at the identified sources.

As shown in Section 5, the present framework is suitable for learning about different aspects of the source distribution such as seasonal patterns, geographic distribution and source type. However, we reiterate that the applicability of our posterior inference to any microplastic particle beached anywhere along the GoA coastline is limited by the extent to which the Nurdle Patrol surveys represent the beaching events across the region. In case these surveys over- or undersample beaching events that take place in a certain part of the domain and/or during a certain time of the year, posterior learning for source attribution will be affected by that sampling bias. If a more comprehensive data on beaching events is available, that can easily be incorporated in the present framework.

We like to mention one aspect of the backtracking simulation and source attribution exercise that offers scope of further research. The simulated trajectories of the virtual particles can broadly be classified into two groups: (i) ones that stay in the ocean cells for entire six months period, and (ii) ones that move through the ocean cells to reach some coastal cell. Since all points on all trajectories are considered as potential source (in terms of location as well as time), this could potentially inflate the relative frequency of ocean cells as source locations resulting in higher posterior contribution from fishing activities that we have seen in Table 1. This limitation arises from the fact, whereas the ocean velocity field data is being used in Equation (3.2) to stochastically determine the spatial trajectory, no such auxiliary information exists that can be used to control the temporal trajectory, i.e., how long the simulation should be run for any given particle. This can be addressed by incorporating information on other features of the beached nurdles such as age, size, polymer type. Age represents the time spent by a particle in the ocean from its source to beaching destination. Microplastics in the open ocean can experience different forces during their lifetime that cause them to degrade. As Van Duinen et al. (2022) notes, age of a beached microplastic particle can be estimated from its state of degradation. Currently, the likelihood calculation in our method treats all points on any simulated trajectory as equally likely. If additional information is available on estimated age distribution of a nurdle, that can be used to reweigh these points (on the temporal scale) accordingly which will in turn change the likelihood calculation and improve the uncertainty associated with source attribution.

Another direction for potential improvement lies in how a virtual particle’s trajectory is simulated in Section 3.1. Here, particle transport was only modeled in 2D, neglecting upswelling and sinking. Also, windage, particle degradation, and resuspension of beached particles were not explicitly modeled. Different particle advection scenarios can be considered in future, conditional on availability of more detailed hydrodynamics information and feasibility of computation.

The time window used for computing the likelihood can be adjusted according to the focus of the study. Computing the likelihood with smaller time windows can lead to an increase in variability. We assessed temporal variability in terms of monthly windows since choosing weeks or days would make the inference too unstable. However, any inference related to particle age necessitates working with daily windows since particles were only tracked for six months, and most particles were beached within 30 days.

To reduce uncertainty of the posterior inference on source locations and times from our model, we would take the following approaches. First, we would release multiple virtual particle per nurdle leading to a proportional increase in simulated trajectories from the current beaching locations. This would allow us to quantify uncertainty associated with possible transport routes between the source and the beaching events. Second, we would extend the temporal domain beyond three years for both the beaching data and the hydrodynamic data. A longer temporal domain would lead to more consistent inference on the available paths between the source and the beaching locations. This would imply data from more beaching locations, again increasing the sample size for the number of virtual particles released. It would also allow us to analyze longer advection times in the GoA. Lastly, if more input data was provided for the GoA that included primary microplastics directly, the incongruity between primary and secondary source locations in our model could be resolved. However, this would require extensive computation on larger datasets (hydrodynamic, prior inputs or beaching data) over the temporal domain, which does not yet exist for the GoA at the resolution used in this article.

The Bayesian approach has the advantage of easily being updated if new information becomes available. In this study, the data used for prior elicitation were taken from global plastic estimates to assess primary and secondary microplastic sources based on the beaching patterns of primary plastics. Often, microplastics are considered secondary microplastics since identifying the source amounts of primary plastics from surveys and models is difficult. In fact, there are no verified estimates for how many primary microplastics enter the marine environment (Boucher and Friot, 2017). However, these estimates could be provided if survey data was done near the watersheds of pellet factories in the GoA. Furthermore, if this type of research were continued for a years-long time span, this methodology could be used to monitor plastic input and identify possible plastic pollution anomalies in the case of extreme weather events (e.g., hurricanes or floods) or manufacturing/shipping accidents.

This article highlights the need for more collection and survey studies on microplastics to understand the full scope of plastic debris. The amount of plastic that enters the marine environment globally is expected to nearly triple by 2060 (Lebreton and Andrady, 2019). Therefore, regions such as the GoA should be of significant interest for researchers to study and monitor microplastics in all environments. Beyond the GoA, other worldwide databases such as the Worldwide Nurdle Hunt (Fidra, 2023) provide similar data for beached nurdles. Hopefully, our framework could be used on current worldwide nurdle estimates to gain valuable knowledge on the potential impact of primary microplastic pollution on terrestrial and marine environments.

Finally, the spatial and temporal nature of microplastic source, transport and beaching events provide ample opportunity for development of sophisticated hierarchical models. For example, one may utilize space-time smoothing on the observed nurdle counts to predict

the beaching events across the entire GoA coastline that would in turn result in more comprehensive source attribution. Similarly, use of dynamic models can be explored for a better description of the underlying physics of plastic transport in the ocean. Managing computational load that usually comes with a fine spatiotemporal grid is another notable challenge. We expect that the present work will draw more attention to this field leading to significant methodological and computational contributions.

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Appendix

A.1 An Illustrative Example of Likelihood Calculation

We present an illustrative example for the method of likelihood calculation based on simulated trajectories. For this example, we consider a subdomain \mathcal{A} consisting of 54,980 gridcells within $[97.98^\circ W, 84^\circ W] \times [22^\circ N, 31.9^\circ N]$ for the 12 temporal windows in $\mathcal{W} = \{\text{March 2019, April 2019, \dots, February 2020}\}$. Let Ξ_n be the set of $n = 1,765$ particles contained within the subdomain and $d = 6$ months.

Now, let us consider an event where a microplastic particle is beached at a bin near Galveston Bay, denoted as $B = A_{s'}$, during September 2019. We want to find the likelihood of that beaching event given that particle was sourced at the Mississippi Delta River mouth bin, denoted as $M = A_s$, during $W_\eta = \text{August 2019}$. This probability can be computed using Equation (3.4) of the main article as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P[\text{beaching event at } A_{s'} \text{ during 09/19} \mid \text{source event at } A_s \text{ in 08/19}] \\
 &= N_{s',\eta'}(s,\eta) / \sum_{a=1}^{54980} \sum_{b:W_b=08/19}^{02/20} N_{a,b}(s,\eta), \tag{A.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the numerator is the number of location-time pairs inside M in August 2019 from trajectories that beach on B in September 2019, and the denominator is the total number of location-time pairs inside M in August 2019 from trajectories that beach anywhere in \mathcal{A} between August 2019 and February 2020 (which is $W_{\eta+d}$). Figure A.1 provides a visual representation of the trajectories relevant to this computation.

Figure A.1: Visualization of trajectories relevant for likelihood calculation using Equation (A.1). There are 146 red trajectories and 13,081 black trajectories. The red trajectories, representing simulated paths where a virtual particle sourced at M (the blue \square , not to scale) during August 2019 beaches at B (the blue \times , not to scale) during September 2019, account for the numerator of the fraction. The red and black trajectories together, representing all simulated paths where a virtual particle sourced at M during August 2019 beaches anywhere in \mathcal{A} between August 2019 and February 2020, account for the denominator. Hence, the numeric value of the expression in Equation (A.1) will be $146/(13081 + 146)$.

A.2 Data and Code Availability

- All code for running and post-processing the GoA simulations are available at https://github.com/davidavzP/BayesianLearning_Microplastics_GoM. Following Python packages have been utilized: xarray (Hoyer and Hamman, 2017), pandas (McKinney, 2010), scipy (Virtanen et al., 2020), matplotlib (Hunter, 2007) and cartopy (Met Office, UK, 2015).
- The code for Parcels is available at <https://www.github.com/OceanParcels/parcels>. The Ocean-Parcels documentation can be accessed at https://docs.oceanparcels.org/en/latest/examples/tutorial_diffusion.html.
- The Nurdle Patrol data are provided by Mission-Aransas National Estuarine Research Reserve, University of Texas Marine Science Institute (Tunnell et al., 2020), and can be downloaded at <https://nurdlepatrol.org/map>.
- The HCOM + NCODA Gulf of Mexico Analysis data are provided by the HYCOM Consortium and can be downloaded at <https://www.hycom.org/data/gomu0pt04/expt-90pt1m000>.
- Global Wave Reanalysis WAVERYS data are provided by the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) and can be downloaded at https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_WAV_001_032/description.
- The data for fishing activities are provided by the Global Fishing Watch and can be found at <https://globalfishingwatch.org/map>.
- The River Plastic Emissions to the World’s Oceans Map by the Ocean Clean Up (Meijer et al., 2021) can be found at <https://theoceancleanup.com/sources/>.